

**MENTAL HEALTH OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN
RELATION TO THEIR JOB STRESS****Hetal Patel***Research Scholar, Gandhi Shikshan Bhavan's Smt. Surajba College of
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College of Education, Mumbai University, Maharashtra***Abstract**

Teaching all over the world is considered as one of the noblest profession. With changing current situations in teaching field, teachers are experiencing tremendous toll on their mental health. The study aimed at finding out the relationship between mental health and job stress among secondary school teachers on the basis of gender and types of school board. Methodology used was descriptive of survey type. Mental Health tool constructed by Dr. Sharma and Dr. Siddiqui was used for the research after seeking their permission. Job stress scale was constructed by the researcher. The sample size consists of 610 secondary school teachers. Data was descriptively and inferentially analysed. Mean score of Mental Health on the basis of gender revealed that female secondary school teachers are higher as compare to male secondary school teachers. Mean score of Mental Health on the basis of school board revealed that SSC board secondary school teachers is slightly higher as compare to ICSE board secondary school teachers. For job stress Mean score on the basis of gender revealed that female secondary school teachers are higher as compare to male secondary school teachers. And on the basis of types of school mean score show that of ICSE secondary school teachers is higher as compared to SSC board secondary school teachers. For the inferential analysis Pearson's coefficient correlation test was used to find out relationship between mental health and job stress. It revealed that there is a significant relationship between Mental

health and job stress of female teacher. There is however no significant relationship between mental health and job stress of male teachers. And findings also reveals that there is a significant relationship between Mental health and Job Stress of SSC and ICSE secondary school teachers. Therefore Mental Health plays an important role in reducing Job Stress.

Key words- *Mental Health, Job Stress, ICSE and SSC secondary school teachers, Female and Male Teachers.*

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Introduction

The education system has changed completely now a day's, being teacher does not mean only being a helper in the difficult process of getting an education; it means being the highly talented guide, which accompanies a student in all way of studying and achieving excellence. The rapid changes and increased complexity of today's world pressurize new challenges and put different demands on school teachers. To maintain high standard of education quality there are chances that it will take a toll on teacher's mental health in order to adjust and cope up with new challenges. Affected mental health further leads to job stress in school teachers.

Mental Health

In the present world of professional competence, everyone is threatened by increasing competitions and degraded circumstances. The concept of health has been extended beyond the proper functioning of the body; it includes controlled emotions, a sound and efficient mind. In simple words it means that mind and body both should work efficiently and harmoniously (Kaur, 2007). Thus, mental health refers to full and harmonious functioning of our total personality as well as to our bio-socio-psychological and spiritual wellbeing. Mental health is far more than the absence of mental illness. Happiness, peace of mind, satisfaction in achievement and enjoyment of life are all aspects of mental health. A person who has good mental health adjusts well with himself and his environment.

Job Stress

Stress is derived from the Latin word '**stringere**' which means to be drawn tight. Stress is defined as a dynamic condition in which an individual is confronted with an opportunity, constraint, or demand related to what he or she desires and for which the outcome is perceived to be uncertain and important. is a chronic disease caused by conditions in the workplace that

negatively affect an individual performance and overall wellbeing of his body and mind. (Robbins,2001) One or more of a host of physical and mental illness manifests job stress. Stress at work is a phenomenon of modern lifestyles. Job stress is a problem in almost all the countries of the world, irrespective of whether the economy is strong or weak. In most of the cases, stress leads to reduced efficiency in even the best of the individuals, which in turn leads to reduced productivity.

Review Of Related Literature

Lamba (2020) studied ‘**Psychological Well-Being and Mental Health Problems in College Teachers and School teachers**’ *reported that the male school teachers have a better psychological well-being and they have a less mental health problem which indicates that if an individual have a less mental health problems then they have better psychological well-being and are more satisfied with their lives. These findings can be used in Indian context and thus essential steps can be taken to educate the people to make their lives better. They can be made aware of the implications of the mental health problems.*

Maheshwari (2019) studied ‘**A study of mental health among private and government school teachers**’ result has shown that (1) There is no significant difference in the mean score of mental health among the government school teachers and private school teachers, (2) There is no significant difference in the mean score of mental health among male and female school teachers and (3) There is significant difference in the interactive effect of the mean scores of mental health with regards to the type of school teachers and gender. Therefore, it could be said that, the female private school teachers group is having good mental health than male private school teachers group.

Braeunig (2018) assessed ‘**Factors influencing mental health improvements in school teachers**’ results revealed that decreases in willingness to work to exhaustion , in striving for perfection , and in the tendency for resignation in the face of failure , as well as an increase of distancing ability and of inner calm and balance appear to be the main factors influencing health improvement in the intervention. Simultaneously, an increase of satisfaction with life is observed. Therefore, the balanced use of professional resources is a critical ingredient in maintaining teachers' health.

Dhar and Magotra (2018) ‘**Compared Occupational Stress Among Teachers Teaching in JKBOSE & CBSE in Jammu District**’ revealed that teachers from JKBOSE and CBSE differ

significantly on various stress-related areas such as role over-load, role ambiguity, role conflict, group and political pressures responsibility for persons, under-participation, powerlessness and poor peer relations.

Harmsen, Helms, Maulana and Veen (2018) examined ‘**The relationship between beginning teachers’ stress causes, stress responses, teaching behaviour and attrition.** indicates that teachers experienced negative pupil behaviour are directly related to tension, negative emotions and discontent among teachers. Relationships with pupils are the basic thing for teachers, if efforts are made to improve this relationship then teacher stress, attrition and the negative effect of stress can be control.

Dua and Sagwan (2017) conducted a ‘**Study on Stress among Female High School Teachers of Haryana**’ revealed that female teachers are more vulnerable to stress as stress is caused by many factors including poor working conditions, scarcity of resources, heavy workloads and lack of administrative and family support system. As a result of these stressful aspects of teaching, stress can have negative effects on teacher’s physical, emotional, behavioural and mental well-being.

Aim Of The Study

To find out relationship between mental health and job stress of secondary school teachers.

Objectives Of The Study

- To ascertain the relationship between mental health and job stress of female secondary school teachers.
- To ascertain the relationship between mental health and job stress of male secondary school teachers.
- To ascertain the relationship between mental health and job stress of SSC board secondary school teachers.
- To ascertain the relationship between mental health and job stress of ICSE secondary school teachers.

Hypothesis Of The Study

- There is no significant relationship between mental health and job stress of female secondary school teachers.
- There is no significant relationship between mental health and job stress of male secondary

school teachers.

- There is no significant relationship between mental health and job stress of SSC board secondary school teachers.
- There is no significant relationship between mental health and job stress of ICSE board secondary school teachers.

Delimitations Of The Study

- The study was conducted in SSC board and ICSE board schools of Mumbai district only.
- The study was delimited to 610 secondary school teachers.

Research Methodology

Methodology Of The Study

The study is of the quantitative descriptive type. It is also correlational type because it deals with the present status of mental health of secondary school teachers with relation to their job stress.

Sampling

The sample consisted of teachers from 49 SSC board schools and 34 ICSE board schools of Greater Mumbai, where the medium of instruction is English. The total sample consisted of 610 secondary school teachers. 361 SSC board and 249 ICSE board secondary school teachers. 498 female teachers and 112 male teachers.

Sampling was done into three stage where in first stage schools were selected through stratified sampling and in second stage schools were selected on basis of SSC and ICSE board and in third stage teacher's data were collected by random sampling.

Tool Used

Mental health tool constructed by Prasad corporation (New Delhi) reliability is 0.93 by split half method. Job stress tool constructed by researcher.

Data for this study were collected using a structured questionnaire. The items are were structured using modified 4 points Likert scale of strongly agreed (SA) = 4 point, agreed (A) =3 points, disagreed (D) = 2 points and strongly disagreed (SD) = 1 points. The reverse is the case for a negative statement.

The draft of the tool was given to eight experts from the faculty of education of the Mumbai University, for face and content validation. Base on the comments, suggestions and inputs

made by these experts, the tool was further improved. In order to ascertain the tool reliability, a pilot study was carried out in two SSC board schools. Where it was found that reliability of job stress tool is 0.781 by Split Half method.

Procedure

After administering the tools on the sample, the scoring was done as per the scoring system.

Data Analysis

Data collected for the main study was analysed by descriptive analysis and inferential analysis. To find out relationship between variables Pearson's co-efficient of correlation test was performed.

Result

Descriptive Analysis For Mental Health

Sample size		Mean	Median	Mode	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness
Female	498	148	143	140	18.561	3.687	1.024
Male	112	143.95	140.5	139	13.896	5.817	1.953
SSC Board	361	147.84	141	139	19.584	2.644	1.864
ICSE Board	249	146.65	143	140	15.083	5.459	1.803

Interpretation: Mean value of mental health indicates that mental health of female secondary school teachers is higher as compare to male secondary school teachers. Similarly SSC board secondary school teachers mental health is marginally higher as compare to ICSE board secondary school teachers.

Descriptive Analysis For Job Stress

Sample size		Mean	Median	Mode	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness
Female	498	88.57	90	94	9.092	-0.296	-0.116
Male	112	87.54	88	94	8.480	-0.0431	-0.140
SSC Board	361	87.54	88	85	9.685	-0.486	-0.047
ICSE Board	249	89.56	91	91	7.711	-0.241	-0.018

Interpretation: Mean value of job stress indicates that job stress of female secondary school teachers is slightly higher as compare to male secondary school teachers. Similarly the job

stress of ICSE secondary school teachers is higher as compared to SSC board secondary school teachers.

Inferential Analysis

- **For hypothesis 1.** There is no significant relationship between mental health and job stress of female secondary school teachers.

Table no.1: Mental Health and Job Stress of female secondary school teachers.

Sample size	Df	'r'	l.o.s	Result
498	496	0.442	Significant at 0.01	Hypothesis rejected

Interpretation of 'r': The coefficient of correlation between mental health and job stress of female secondary school teachers is 0.442, which is positive, shows strong positive relationship and significant at 0.01 level. Hence null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion for hypotheses 1. There is a relationship between mental health and job stress of female secondary school teachers.

Discussion: The positive, strong relationship between mental health and job stress of secondary school teachers for the female teachers indicates that job stress in teaching profession greatly have an impact on female teachers. Teaching profession can be identified as a stressful occupation in this modern challenging world which can adversely affect the mental health of the teachers which in turn affects the students and the learning environment. In this respect, female school teachers usually faced lots of occupational stress as they have to play multiple roles both at homes and schools.

- **For hypothesis 2.** There is no significant relationship between mental health and job stress of male secondary school teachers.

Table no.2: Mental Health and Job Stress of male secondary school teachers.

Sample size	Df	'r'	l.o.s	Result
112	110	0.127	Not significant	Hypothesis accepted

Interpretation of 'r': The coefficient of correlation between mental health and job stress of male secondary school teachers is 0.127, which is positive, shows no relationship and not significant at 0.01 level. Hence null hypothesis is accepted

Conclusion for hypotheses 2. There is no relationship between mental health and job stress

of male secondary school teachers.

Discussion: No relationship between mental health and job stress indicates that male report different reactions to stress, both physically and mentally. Male teachers attempt to manage stress in very different ways and also perceive their ability to do so and the things that stand in their way in markedly different ways. Male teachers experienced significantly lower levels of occupational stress, specifically with regard to interaction with students and colleagues, workload, students' progress and emotional exhaustion as they are emotionally more stable.

- **For hypothesis 3.** There is no significant relationship between mental health and job stress of SSC board secondary school teachers.

Table no.3: Mental Health and Job Stress of SSC board secondary school teachers.

Sample size	Df	'r'	l.o.s	Result
361	359	0.316	Significant at 0.01	Hypothesis rejected

Interpretation of 'r': The coefficient of correlation between mental health and job stress of SSC board secondary school teachers is 0.316, which is positive, shows moderate positive relationship and significant at 0.01 level. Hence null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion for hypotheses 3. There is a moderate relationship between mental health and job stress of SSC board secondary school teachers.

Discussion: The positive, moderate relationship between mental health and job stress of secondary school teachers from SSC board schools indicates that job stress in teaching profession is affecting mental health very badly. The reason behind this can be degrading conditions of SSC board schools in Mumbai as compared to other boards. Teachers experienced higher levels of burnout, specifically in terms of emotional exhaustion and disengagement from the profession, problems in interaction with students, lack of interest, low attainment and handling students with "difficult" behaviour.

- **For hypothesis 4.** There is no significant relationship between mental health and job stress of ICSE board secondary school teachers.

Table no.4: Mental Health and Job Stress of ICSE board secondary school teachers.

Sample size	Df	'r'	l.o.s	Result
249	247	0.283	Significant at 0.01	Hypothesis rejected

Interpretation of 'r': The coefficient of correlation between mental health and job stress of ICSE board secondary school teachers is 0.283, which is positive, shows weak positive relationship and significant at 0.01 level. Hence null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion for hypotheses 4. There is a weak positive relationship between mental health and job stress of ICSE board secondary school teachers.

Discussion: The positive, weak relationship between mental health and job stress of secondary school teachers from ICSE board schools indicates that job stress in teaching profession is affecting mental health very badly. Secondary school teachers from ICSE board are facing serious problem of job stress largely due to work overload, over expectation, time management, less payment, lack of motivation and students' indiscipline which is leading to poor job performance, anxiety, boredom and prostration.

Conclusion

It revealed that there is a significant relationship between Mental health and job stress of female teacher. There is however no significant relationship between mental health and job stress of male teachers. And findings also reveals that there is a significant relationship between Mental health and Job Stress of SSC and ICSE secondary school teachers. Therefore Mental Health plays an important role in reducing Job Stress.

Suggestions

Suggestions to improve mental health of teachers

Building supportive cultures in school, reduced workload, mindfulness, advance planning, ,cultivate a positive mind set, create a vision board, set reasonable expectations (for yourself and others), model self-compassion, reconnect to your purpose of teaching, adopt a growth mind set in your teaching, focus on kindness towards students and gratitude, create clear boundaries between home and school, set up effective debriefing and mentoring structures, , build up your emotional resilience, keep focused on your goals, build new connections and relationships related to teaching profession.

Suggestion to reduce job stress of teachers.

Work out priorities, identify your stress situations in school, don't react to imagined insults, think before you commit to any school work, move on if you made any mistake, don't dwell on past mistakes, don't bottle up anger & frustrations towards any person in school, help students to cope with stress, think positively, ask for help from your school

members, make a connection with colleague, focus on what is in your control, notice energizers and drainers in school and learn to say no when you are not able to match up their expectation.

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